

EVALUATION OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CF/AL COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY LOW PRESSURE INFILTRATION METHOD

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Keywords: *CF/Al composites, Low pressure infiltration, Thermal conductivity*

1 Introduction

In the electronic packaging component fields, the composite materials with high thermal conductivity (TC) and light weight have been expected to utilize as heatsink materials for the electronic parts of high heat generation [1, 2]. On the other hand, coal-tar pitch based carbon fibers (CFs) possess high thermal and electrical conductivity and good mechanical properties. In addition, the coal-tar pitch based CF reinforced Al composites can be one of the promising materials for the heatsink components with high TC, light weight and good machining.

Moreover, the low pressure infiltration (LPI) method is the useful fabrication process for composite materials by molten metal infiltration with some atmospheric pressures into porous fiber preform. The LPI method enables to fabricate the composite materials with cost saving, large or complex structure [3, 4].

However, the CF/Al composites inevitably contain Al_4C_3 at the fiber-matrix interface by chemical reaction between the CF and Al. Many attempts have been made to characterize the Al_4C_3 in both chemical and mechanical fields [5-7]. It was known that the generation and growth of Al_4C_3 by chemical reaction happened at the temperature above 773 K with the duration time. In the LPI process for CF/Al composites, Al_4C_3 could easily generate after infiltration of molten Al into porous CF preform, especially cooling process. The Al_4C_3 is able to give a bad effect to the TC of CF/Al composites. Moreover, alloying element such as Cu in the Al-based matrix is also able to degrade the TC of CF/Al composites.

In the present study, the TC of the coal-tar pitch

based unidirectional CF/Al composites by LPI process have been investigated. Especially, the influence of the interfacial reactants on the TC of CF/Al composites was discussed in the viewpoint of the damage of carbon fibers. Moreover, the effect of addition element in the matrix such as Cu on the TC of the matrix was evaluated.

2 Experimental Procedures

Prior to carry out the LPI process for CF/Al composites, the porous CF preform has been prepared as follows: The CF mixture was prepared by dispersing 10 vol% Cu powder (Hukuda metal, foil & powders Co, Ltd.) into the 30 vol% coal tar pitch based unidirectional K13D2U CFs (Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc.) bundles with polyethyleneglycol (PEG) as a dispersant. Subsequently, the CF mixture was sintered to be the CF preform by the spark plasma sintering (SPS) method to burn the PEG out and bridge the Cu particles between CFs. The sintering conditions of SPS were current and voltage of 390 A and 4 V and temperature of 1123 K during 30 min under vacuum. The CF/Al composites were fabricated by LPI process with applied pressure of 0.8 MPa at the temperature of 1073 K under Ar atmosphere. Especially, the cooling conditions after infiltration were 10, 20 and 30 min at the temperature range from 1073 K to 773 K.

The amount of the interfacial reactant such as Al_4C_3 in the CF/Al composites was measured from the 'weight loss of the CF/Al composites' by removing CH_4 gas generated in accordance with chemical reaction of Al_4C_3 and distilled water. The 'weight loss of CF' was calculated from the creation amount of Al_4C_3 . The CFs was extracted from the

CF/Al composites by immersing the composites in 10% 2N HCl aqueous solution in order to observe the CF surfaces by SEM.

The TCs of CF/Al composites were evaluated by laser-flash method (TC-7000, Ulvac-Riko, Inc.) on parallel and perpendicular direction of fiber axis. The TC of matrix such as Al-35wt% Cu alloy was also examined by laser-flash method. The Al-Cu alloy was fabricated by SPS process of pure Al and Cu powders with same cooling condition as the LPI process of CF/Al composites. Moreover, the TC of the Al-Cu alloys and artificially aged Al-Cu alloys at 463 K during 12 hr was also measured by 4-probe electrical resistance measurement technique.

3 Results and Discussion

In order to characterize the TC of unidirectional CF/Al composites, the comprehensive TC properties such as matrix and longitudinal and transverse direction of the unidirectional CF/Al composites have been investigated, in conjunction with their theoretical values calculated by rule of mixture (ROM) of the CF and matrix. Fig. 1 exhibits the TC of the CF/Al composites and their matrix by laser-flash method at room temperature. The matrix and composites were fabricated with the cooling time of 10 min, at the temperature range from 1073 K to 773K after sintering and infiltration, respectively. The initial CF possessed the high longitudinal TC of about $800 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ which was offered from company. Besides, the TC of the matrix such as Al-35wt%Cu alloy was as $71.7 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ in this experiment. The TC of matrix was lower than not only the TC of the industrial pure Al such as A 1070 ($234 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) but also the TC data of Al-Cu alloy in reference [8]. The characteristics of the TC on the Al-Cu alloys will be discussed later.

The 30 vol% CF/Al composites represented the longitudinal TC of $273.2 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. The longitudinal TC of composites was corresponding to 94 % of the theoretical value. It can be supposed that the heat was individually conducted to CFs and matrix on longitudinal direction of composites without the heat loss by fiber-matrix interface reaction. In the meantime, the transverse direction of CF/Al composites shows low TC of $48.0 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. It can be also supposed that the heat is mainly conducted through the matrix because the transverse direction of the K13D2U CF may have extremely low TC, which is based on the transverse TC ($2.4 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)

Fig. 1 Thermal conductivity of longitudinal and transverse direction of CF/Al composites and matrix.

of the K-1100 (BP Amoco Chemicals) with similar fiber internal structure. Meanwhile, the transverse TC was corresponding to 96 % of theoretical value, which was calculated by ROM with disregarding the transverse TC of the CF. It is obvious from these results that the interfacial reactant such as Al_4C_3 has any remarkable bad effects on both direction of TC. Especially, the nucleation and growth of Al_4C_3 by the interfacial reaction depended on the fabrication process such as the exposure time at the temperature above 773 K. Moreover, the cooling time of 10 min was too short to generate enough amount of Al_4C_3 to influence on the TC of composites

On the other hand, it is assumed that the Al_4C_3 , sufficiently generated at interface between fiber-matrix, is able to give a decisive effect on the TC of composites from the viewpoint of the CF degradation. The correlation between the cooling time at LPI process and the TC of CF/Al composites was shown in Fig. 2. With increasing cooling time, the longitudinal TC of composites was significantly decreased, whereas the transverse TC was not affected by cooling time mostly. In fact, the increase of fiber-matrix reaction time led to increase the amount of Al_4C_3 and simultaneously decrease the weight of CF. Since the unidirectional CF has high TC of parallel direction to the fiber axis, the longitudinal TC is more sensitive on the weight loss of CF than transverse direction. In the close inspection of the weight loss of the CF, the CF in

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Fig. 2 Thermal conductivity of longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CF/Al composites depending on the cooling time at LPI process.

composites had lost their weight according to the increase of the cooling time, as shown in Fig. 3. The weight loss of CF was 0.09, 0.19 and 0.34 wt% according to the increasing cooling time of 10, 20 and 30 min, respectively. It is doubtless that the weight loss of the CF in composites is a main reason of decreasing longitudinal TC of composites. However, the amount of the weight loss was very little. If the Al_4C_3 by interfacial reaction occurred like the uniform layer on the CF surface, the cross-sectional area reduction of the CF was insensible. In other words, such area reduction of the CF was not suitable to account for the significant longitudinal TC loss of composites.

Indeed, according to the SEM observation of the extracted CF from composites, Al_4C_3 by interfacial reaction might be not generated with the uniform layer, as shown in Fig. 4. All of the CF surfaces (Fig. 4 (b)-(d)) depending on the cooling time of 10, 20 and 30 min were damaged by the generation of Al_4C_3 , in comparison with the initial CF (Fig. 4(a)). In case of Fig. 4 (b), the small and spot-like fiber damages at local area of CF surface was observed because of the short duration of cooling time as 10 min. The spot-like fiber damage might be caused by the growth of the needle-like shaped Al_4C_3 from the CF surface to the Al matrix. Of course the short duration of fiber-matrix reaction time is expected to limit the generation of Al_4C_3 . Such small damages might not affect much to decrease the longitudinal TC of the composites severely. However, there were

Fig. 3 Weight loss of carbon fiber in unidirectional CF/Al composites depending on the cooling time at LPI process.

shown the remarkable fiber surface damages in Fig. 4 (c) and (d) according to increasing cooling time of 20 and 30 min. The locally and harshly damaged CF surface was able to disturb the effective heat flow to the parallel direction of the fiber axis, due to become the locally and drastically narrow cross-sectional area of the CF. The shrunken cross-sectional area of CF is considered a main reason of deteriorating longitudinal TC of composites severely.

The factors giving the bad influence on the TC of composites are not only generation of Al_4C_3 by interfacial reaction but also alloying elements in matrix. Fig. 5 exhibits the TC of Al-Cu alloys. The constituent of matrix in CF/Al composites was consistent with Al- 35wt% Cu. Each Al-Cu alloy was fabricated by SPS method with the same cooling time of 10 min as LPI process. The Al-Cu alloys typically have lower TC than pure Al because of precipitation of the Al-Cu intermetallic phases in α -Al. The intermetallic phase such as $CuAl_2$ in Al-Cu alloys usually plays a role of the thermal resistance to the heat flow with its low TC. For this reason, the TCs of Al-Cu alloys decreased to 149.3, 109.3 and 86.9 $Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$ depending on the increasing Cu addition of 4.5, 24 and 35 wt%, respectively. However, the Al-Cu alloys in this experiment have relatively low TC in comparison with the TC of reference [8]. This is considered that the supersaturated solid solution of Cu in α -Al, which was caused by relatively rapid cooling time of 10 min, obstructed to effective thermal conduction

Fig. 4 Microstructure of carbon fiber surface; (a) initial fiber and (b), (c) and (d) damaged surfaces depending on the cooling time of (b) 10, (c) 20 and (d) 30 min at LPI process.

Fig. 5 Thermal conductivity of Al-Cu alloys depending on the composition ratio of Al-Cu and their heat treatment.

through α -Al. It means that the cause of decreasing TC of the matrix was not only CuAl_2 but also supersaturated solid solution of Cu. According to the reference of [9-12], the electrical resistance of alloys decreased with precipitation of the alloying element in the base metal by heat treatment. The decrease of electrical resistance means the increase of thermal conductivity as well as electrical conductivity by Wiedemann-Franz law. The TC of matrix can be also improved by heat treatment with promoting the phase transformation from the supersaturated solid solution of Cu in α -Al to stable CuAl_2 phases. Fig. 5 also represents the promoted TCs of Al-Cu alloys by artificial ageing at 463 K during 12 hr. As a result of ageing, the TC of aged Al- 35wt% Cu alloys improved about 18 % of the previous one.

4 Conclusions

The coal-tar pitch based unidirectional CF/Al composites were fabricated by LPI process with the

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different cooling time of 10, 20 and 30 min at the temperature range from 1073 K to 773 K. The TC of CF/Al composites with cooling time of 10 min represented 94 % and 96 % of theoretical value in longitudinal and transverse direction without any effects of interfacial reactant such as Al_4C_3 .

However, the increase of cooling time led to decrease of the longitudinal TC of CF/Al composites. The increase of the Al_4C_3 amount in the interface with increase of cooling time led to the weight loss of the CFs. Consequently, high longitudinal TC of the CFs was sensitive to the weight loss of CFs. Although the amount of weight loss was very little to decrease the TC of composites that much, in fact the CF surface by the generation of Al_4C_3 was locally damaged. Therefore, the locally damaged area of the CF surface played a role of a notch to flow the heat difficultly. On the other hand, the matrix such as Al-35 wt% Cu alloy had low TC because of the existence of not only $CuAl_2$ but also supersaturated solid solution of Cu in α -Al. The TC of Al-35 wt% Cu alloy with the artificial ageing at 463 K during 12 hr improved by the phase transformation from the supersaturated solid solution of Cu in α -Al to stable $CuAl_2$ phases.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the light metal educational foundation in Japan and Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (c) (21560771) from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan and the high technological research project on "Research and Development Center for Advanced Composite Materials" of Doshisha University and the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan.

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